

Tourism programs

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Abstract:

We are going to create an application We will call (Wejhh), to support domestic tourism. In this application, people organize a tour around Oman. In this application people select where they are and where they want to go and for how many days. Also, possibility to stop in more than one place, then they will choose where they want to stay indoors or outdoors. for example, they want to stay in a hotel or want to camp or they want to star in a caravan. In addition, they can select if they want meals during these days and what kind of food and restaurants they prefer. if they want to roast we can organize for them everything they want. Related to the activities that they are interested like marine activities and hiking or cycling. We can prepare for their special occasions like birthdays. Foreigners can choose a tour guide Translator or driver and photographer. Among the tourist schedules provided by the application are trips to tourist and traditional places and various events for some occasions such as National Day and Omani Women’s Day, in addition to experiencing the region’s costume and experiencing some of the customs that it is famous for. The mission of the app is to design a tour schedule that suits people and contains all the tourist attractions in the area that most people do not know about it. For emergencies, they can contact the police directly by sending the location from the application.